

U-937 (CRL-1593.2) Protocol

Description:

- **Organism:** Homo sapiens, human
- **Tissue:** Pleural effusion
- **Morphology:** monocyte
- **Age:** 37 years
- **Ethnicity:** white
- **Gender:** male
- **Derivation:** U-937 cell line was derived by Sundstrom and Nilsson in 1974 from malignant cells obtained from the pleural effusion of a patient with histiocytic lymphoma
- **Immortalization method:** Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) transformed
- **BSL 1**
- **Growth properties:** suspension
- **Expression markers:** complement (C3)
- **Comments:** studies since 1979 have shown that U-937 cells can be induced to terminal monocytic differentiation by supernatants from human mixed lymphocyte cultures. The cells are negative for immunoglobulin production and Epstein-Barr virus expression. The cells express the Fas antigen and are sensitive to TNF and anti-Fas antibodies.

Complete medium:

- RPMI-1640 medium
- 10% FBS
- 1% Penicillin/Streptomycin
- 1% L-glutamine

Reagents for cryopreservation:

Complete growth medium supplemented with 5% DMSO.

Thawing the cells:

1. Thaw the vial by gentle agitation in a 37°C water bath. Warning: to reduce the possibility of contamination, keep the O-ring and cap out of the water.
Thawing should be rapid (approximately 2')
2. Remove the vial from the water bath as soon as the contents are thawed and decontaminate by dipping in or spraying with 70% ethanol. All the operations from this point on should be carried out under strict aseptic conditions
3. Transfer the vial contents to a centrifuge tube containing 9 mL complete culture medium and spin at 125 xg for 5-7'
4. Resuspend cell pellet with the recommended complete medium
5. Incubate the culture at 37°C in a suitable incubator

Subculturing procedure:

Growth properties: suspension

Cultures can be maintained by the addition of fresh medium or replacement of medium. Alternatively, cultures can be established by centrifugation with subsequent resuspension at 1 to 2×10^5 viable cells/mL.

Interval: maintain cell density between 1×10^5 and 2×10^6 viable cells/mL

Medium Renewal: add fresh medium every 3 to 4 days (depending on cell density)

ATCC Number: **CRL-1593.2**™
Designation: **U-937**

Low Density

Scale Bar = 100µm

High Density

Scale Bar = 100µm